

The use of participatory methodologies for conducting literacy activities:

A perfect but not explicit fit

Juan D. Machin-Mastromatteo

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Purpose: To construct the basis for a research agenda that integrates participatory methodologies (PM) into literacies (L) research and practice as a valuable methodological basis. **Design/methodology/approach:** The pros and cons of using PM on L research and practice are explained, as well as its possibilities, characteristics and the contributions of a research agenda under such integration (PM-L agenda). This analysis draws from the pertinent literature, Scopus publication data, our own practice as IL researchers, and a questionnaire used to gather further insights from the research community in this matter. **Findings:** A further understanding of the contributions that a PM-L research agenda can bring to the Library and Information Science field is achieved. The pros, cons, hesitations and eagerness that researchers might have toward the idea of using such integration are valuable to determine if this really is a perfect but not explicit fit. **Research limitations/implications:** Although the questionnaire was promoted in a large international conference during a four-year period (2013-2017), it was answered by 34 participants; but only 16 of them had previous experiences with the PM-L integration, and only an average of 8 participants provided significant answers to our open-ended questions; so, the amount of data available to analyze was limited. Certainly, using Scopus data provides a large but incomplete picture of the specialized literature that is peer-reviewed and indexed, because it excludes publications not indexed that may be pertinent. **Originality/value:** The PM-L integration is deemed as highly adequate, as PM seek to improve participants' conditions, situations and realities through reflection and engagement; while L-related activities and research (including information, digital, media literacy, or new literacies) are conducted to improve people's use and understanding of the media for which they are developing literacy. This contributes to their betterment as critical-thinkers, persons, citizens and learners. However, many researchers and especially practitioners do not formally use PM to conduct L activities, at least in many cases this is not made explicitly. In the case of practitioners, some have conducted such activities empirically, without an appropriate methodological foundation. Hence, to establish PM as the methodologies of choice may help researchers and practitioners to have a stronger methodological basis to conduct their work.

Keywords: action research, participatory action research, information literacy, research, practice, participatory methodologies

Article Classification: Research paper

Introduction

This paper offers directions toward constructing the basis for a research agenda that integrates participatory methodologies into literacies research and practice as a valuable methodological basis. In order to achieve this purpose, this paper explains the pros and cons of using PM on L research and practice are, as well as its possibilities, characteristics and the contributions of a research agenda

under such integration (PM-L agenda). This analysis draws from the pertinent literature, Scopus publication data, our own practice as IL researchers, and a questionnaire used to gather further insights from the research community in this matter and to strengthen our analysis.

The term participatory methodologies (PM) refers to various methodological traditions that have emerged from action research, such as participatory action research (PAR). PM share unique characteristics that are explained in the literature review section, for instance, they emphasize the use of actions or interventions in research, individuals' participation and engagement throughout the research process, they stress that research is conducted with people rather than on people, they study participants' practices, reactions, reflection, and impressions; and they also allow the researcher to participate and intervene, instead of being the traditional so-called 'fly on the wall'. These methodologies seek to improve upon participants' conditions, situations and realities through reflection and engagement.

The umbrella term literacies (L) is used to include various related terms, which also represent related research areas, namely: digital literacy (DL), new literacies (NL), media literacy (ML), or media and information literacy (MIL). Such handling of the terms was taken from previous research (Machin-Mastromatteo, 2012; Machin-Mastromatteo, Beltran & Lau, 2014) that drew from the specialized literature (e.g. Lau, 2006; Gee, 2007; Lankshear and Knobel, 2007; Lankshear and Knobel, 2011; Knobel and Lankshear, 2016) to seek a relationship and conciliation of terms, while providing short definitions for each of them. IL is broadly defined as the individual's ability to handle information in general. DL refers to the ability to handle technological devices (hardware and software), as well as the ability to determine the quality and accuracy of digital information. NL are a series of new and innovative skills associated to ways of working with online content, social technologies, and videogames, thus, going beyond the concept of DL. ML and MIL are similar because they focus in developing media literate individuals, which is important in this 'fake news' era; although only MIL explicitly considers information within its focus. ML "is focused on teaching and learning practices to critically interpret, create and act on media messages and media productions" (Phillips, 2017, para. 3). MIL considers information to be important and in parallel to media in its interests and it has been prominent in United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization's working documents, seemingly much more than any other L (see UNESCO, 2017).

All L imply conducting activities to make people literate in different media (information, technologies, and media) for their betterment as critical-thinkers, persons, citizens and learners, which connects greatly with the purpose of PM: improve participants' conditions, situations and realities through reflection and engagement. Hence, L and PM share the essence of being important for improving people's conditions, this is why this paper proposes the use of PM as the methodology of choice for conducting L-related activities, including research, which we are denominating a PM-L integration and research agenda throughout this paper. The need for such integration and the present exploration is justified because many researchers, and especially practitioners, do not formally use PM to conduct L activities, at least in many cases this is not made explicit in their publications or reports. In the case of practitioners, some are used to conduct such activities empirically, without an appropriate methodological foundation. This could be due to not having suitable methodological knowledge or bases (in the case of practitioners), because they do not know about PM, or precisely because they know about them and hesitate to use them in an area that, as many others, have a very strong influence from positivist and quantitative approaches.

Given the shared essence among PM and L, as well as the above statements of PM not being extensively used in L-related activities and research, we argue that PM-L is a perfect but not explicit fit. Hence, we seek to establish PM as the methodologies of choice that may help researchers and practitioners to have a stronger and more consonant methodological basis to conduct their work, as well as establishing PM-L as a valid research agenda.

Literature review

This section includes a brief review of PM as the research methodologies in which we exclusively focus on this paper, specifically action research and PAR, although other branches derived from action research are mentioned. Furthermore, we analyze the 'perfect but not explicit fit' between PM and L, by explaining the pros, cons, hesitations and eagerness that researchers from different methodological traditions might have toward the idea of using PM. A further overview of IL and other L was not deemed necessary beyond the definitions provided in the introduction section above, given space constraints and the scope of this article, which does not require a further discussion or understanding of these concepts in order to present its main topics in an accessible manner.

Participatory Methodologies

Action Research (AR) originated around the 1930s and 1940s with the works of Kurt Lewin (Whitehead & McNiff, 2006), who developed a comprehensive AR theory (Lewin, 1946). Lewin's studies introduced many of the relevant notions that participatory researchers are currently working with, such as: problem solving and knowledge generation, group dynamics, and improving people's conditions from the examination of their realities. Various research traditions were derived from AR, such as action science, PAR, feminist PAR, practitioner research, self-study, and teacher research. While they are all participatory methodologies, some researchers understand them as synonyms, while others consider that there are differences and advocate for the use of one or other of these 'branches'. PAR is an arguably popular branch when presented next to the other ones and some researchers argue that it uniquely stresses participation from all research participants, including the researcher. However, it is interesting to cite a 'classic' AR definition, where the word participatory is also highly stressed:

action research is a participatory, democratic process concerned with developing practical knowing in the pursuit of worthwhile human purposes, grounded in a participatory worldview which we believe is emerging at this historical moment. It seeks to bring together action and reflection, theory and practice, in participation with others, in the pursuit of practical solutions to issues of pressing concern to people, and more generally the flourishing of individual persons and their communities (Reason & Bradbury, 2001: 1).

Definitions such as the one cited above may be among the possible reasons why the terms AR and PAR are often used interchangeably or understood as synonyms. Henceforth, we will combine all methodological traditions that branched out from AR under the term participatory methodologies (PM). PM are mainly qualitative. They require the researcher to implement actions aiming to study the practices, habits, activities or behaviors of participants, with the purpose of helping them achieve a state of improvement over their conditions, situations and realities, through reflection and engagement. PM are conducted in the form of cycles, which involve at least one instance (or one lap) of the following stages: diagnostic or analysis, planning, action or intervention, observation, evaluation and reflection (McTaggart, 1991; Whitehead & McNiff, 2006). These stages may be repeated throughout research until PAR stakeholders are satisfied; or they can be applied continuously, to establish a continuous improvement process. PM imply a collective commitment

toward the study and the improvement of practices or situations, as well as toward the researcher's work, which is conducted with the participants (stressing 'with' as opposed to 'on') from their own knowledge to mediate a common understanding that harmonizes everyone's knowledge, practices and realities (Herr & Anderson, 2015).

Machin-Mastromatteo & Tarango (2019) summarize briefly the epistemological and ontological characteristics of PM. At an epistemological level, there is an interaction between theory and practice, which allows to analyze the improvements that have taken place on the studied situation or people. For such analysis to be possible, one or several actions must be implemented, so their effects can be measured and determined through individual and collective reflection; including the systematic analysis of the researcher. Ontologically, PM do not make a conventional distinction between the research object, subjects, the researcher and the research process. Hence, participatory researchers may take part in the research as the participants, because researchers are expected to take actions that may affect group dynamics and change situations. Apart from analyzing participants' insights, researchers have the possibility of reflecting upon their own actions and practices during their research; and they can systematize this process of reflection to report it as part of their research findings.

Participatory researchers come from different backgrounds, such as management and organizational theory, community development, sociology, education, political science, and library and information science (McIntyre, 2008; Herr & Anderson, 2015). Because of this, PM have been permeated and enhanced by different fields and so they have resulted to be versatile methodologies that are not necessarily based on a unique theoretical framework (McIntyre, 2008). This versatility has also influenced the advantageous possibility of applying many different methods and instruments in a research conducted through PM, including conventional methods and data collection instruments, as well as other less conventional ones (Machin-Mastromatteo & Tarango, 2019). In order to evaluate a participatory research process, conventional methods and data collection instruments, such as questionnaires, surveys, interviews, focus groups and statistical methods can be used. Other methods and instruments may be used, such as learning activities, strategies and interventions; as well as diaries and other documents produced by participants, such as essays, memos, drawings, video or audio recordings (McIntosh, 2010). These latter strategies allow collecting rich and detailed data that the researcher can use to observe, measure and analyze participants' reactions to the research actions and their effects. Further analysis and even triangulation can be performed with the aid of conventional instruments, or an analysis method can be applied to other methods' contents.

PM and L: A perfect but not explicit fit?

Freire's works are arguably among the classic and most popular examples of AR (e.g. Freire, 1970, 1973, 1985) and we can trace to this highly influential author the intention of bridging PM with L. However, his approach dealt more specifically with reading and writing literacy and emancipatory educational models, which emphasized students' active participation and sought to collapse the teacher-student dichotomy.

Researchers have highlighted that PM approaches have been left out and is sometimes dismissed by the education and research community (Fals-Borda, 1992; Walker, 1996; Zeichner, 2009), especially when it is compared to positivist approaches (Williamson, Bellman & Webster, 2011). Arguably, there has been a renewed interest of using PM within the L research fields, which we can observe when analyzing Scopus publication data, through the following specific queries that were conducted in July 2017 (searching within the fields 'Article title', 'Abstract' and 'Keywords'):

- There are 15,671 documents on “action research” from 1946 (oldest indexed document) to 2018 (newest) and 2,878 on “participatory action research” from 1982 to 2018. According to Scopus data, AR is used more often than PAR. For instance, in 2016 PAR documents accounted for the 23.5% of all documents on AR, while this proportion reached 28% for 2017 documents published as of July. Because the queries we used to locate AR and PAR documents have two words in common (action AND research), when we searched for AR, documents on PAR appear in the search results. Conversely, when we searched for PAR documents, AR documents were excluded, because we used exact phrases as search strings. Hence, the final query used to retrieve the results of interest was ‘action research’.
- There are 5,678 documents related to “information literacy” (1975 to 2017), 1,675 to “media literacy” (1985 to 2017), 1,611 to “digital literacy” (1997 to 2017), 847 to “new literacies”, and 76 to “media and information literacy” (2005 to 2017), which are the main L-related concepts of interest for the Library and Information Science field. There are significant differences between the number of results for each of the L of interest. We could have used the search string “literac*”, which would have included literacy and literacies, but this would have retrieved much more results that may not be pertinent for the LIS field (416 to be exact), such as read-write literacy, language literacy, numerical literacy or just the word literacy, even if it was not significant within the contents of a given document.
- There are 113 documents under the query ["action research" AND ("information literacy" OR "digital literacy" OR "new literacies" OR "media literacy" OR "media and information literacy")], from 2000 to 2017; while only 19 documents were retrieved with the query ["participatory action research" AND ("information literacy" OR "digital literacy" OR "new literacies" OR "media literacy" OR "media and information literacy")], from 2001 to 2017. The query starting with “action research” is more inclusive to identify pertinent documents for a PAR-IL agenda, as data shows that not all researchers are using PAR in their documents, but that they prefer to use AR, because of the 113 documents with AR only 19 have PAR in their metadata. This could be due to conceiving both traditions as synonyms and choosing AR instead of PAR, or it might be due to the authors not stressing participation in their research and thus using AR as it would be more appropriate in this case.
- Scopus data shows that publications under these combinations of terms (AR AND the various chosen L) are fairly recent, as the oldest documents are from 2000, so PM-L can be seen as an emerging research area. From the 113 documents combining all terms, 49 refer to IL, 33 to ML, 27 to NL, 25 to DL, and 2 to MIL. The number of publications per year and per each literacy (IL, ML, NL, DL and MIL) can be seen in Figure 1. There are more than 113 entries in the figure, this is due to the fact that each document can mention two or more L in their keywords, titles or abstract. For example, one document can have both IL and DL and hence one entry is counted for each of these literacies. The present document has all five L in its keywords, so it would raise the count for each L by one.

Figure 1. Publications on participatory methodologies and the various literacies per year. Source: Scopus data, retrieved on July 17, 2017

- From the previously mentioned 113 documents, Scopus data indicates that these were published by 158 authors, 134 of them have published only one document, 20 authors have published two. From their number of publications, this is a field led by Machin-Mastromatteo with six documents, then by Bothma, Chen, and Lacasa with three documents each, and by Barden, De Boer, De La Fuente Prieto, Doucet, Fernández-Ramos, Lau, Lotherington, Mahoney, Martínez, Méndez, Petela, Pinto, Ranieri, Scheepers, Somerville, Taylor, Vezzosi, Virkus, Yildiz, and Zenkov with two documents each. The largest number of documents have been published in *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy* (with 15 documents), *Communications in Computer and Information Science* (eight), *Educational Action Research* (three), *New Library World* (three), *Informação e Sociedade* (two), *Journal of Educational Media and Library Science* (two), *Journal of Information Literacy* (two), *Library Review* (two), *Libri* (two), and *Reading and Writing Quarterly* (two); other 53 journals have published one document each.

Certainly, using Scopus data provides a large picture of the specialized literature that is peer-reviewed and indexed. However, such a picture is incomplete, as it ignores theses, books, conference papers and articles that may be pertinent, but that may not be peer-reviewed, indexed or have the quality levels required by Scopus to be indexed. Nevertheless, using Scopus is a better choice than to use Web of Science, as the latter is known for indexing fewer publications and most of the publications indexed in the latter are indexed in the former, but not vice versa.

Given the number of documents indexed in Scopus and their characteristics, we can state that PM have gained recognition in the past years as the methodologies used to conduct research on the various L areas, which are relevant for the LIS field, as evidenced by the choice of having a full entry specifically on PAR in the forthcoming *International Encyclopedia of Media Literacy*, written by Machin-Mastromatteo & Tarango (2019). PM deserve to be revisited as methodologies and its possible applications into the L areas should be analyzed. We argue that PM should be brought forward as particularly useful methodological stances for L research and practice.

We have argued that PM are a perfect but not explicit fit for establishing a methodological basis for L research and practice. They connect in their goals, purposes and general ideals of improving the human being. PM draw attention to the reactive effects of the researcher's presence within a participatory community. They facilitate change and study, analyze and improve individual or groups' practices to achieve a state of betterment or to improve practices. Research participants have a special commitment toward the goal the participatory study, as they must see it as a collaborative endeavor, where the researcher engages participants from his or her own knowledge to mediate common understandings built from the knowledge, practices and realities of all research stakeholders. Participatory researchers may also reflect upon their own practices and achieve a state of personal improvement as well. PM goals are thus emancipatory. Then, L research and practice strives to develop more informed individuals, independent information, technology and media users; as well as critical thinkers that are capable of achieving different purposes, such as: problem solving, decision making, emancipation, the exercise of active citizenship, overcoming oppression, bridging divides, achieving critical stances, and lifelong learning. These purposes have been largely studied since the term IL was coined (Zurkowski, 1974). To make a 'good use' of information for improving the human being is at the heart of IL, so to have a PM stance as a common methodological basis to conduct all L activities seems like a perfect match. However, we believe that the bridging of IL with PAR has only started to be (re)discovered, because of the relatively small number of documents dealing with PM-L. Moreover, an analysis of this connection such as the present may lead to improved research agendas for the L areas, as many L researchers and practitioners may not know about PM and how well they fit into

L research and practice. Hence, as Machin-Mastromatteo, Lau & Virkus (2013) questioned regarding the use of PAR in IL research and practice:

is it time to review some of these and bring them back to the forefront in order to see if an IL research and practice agenda, which integrates PAR, can translate to an enhancement of its results in the coming years? Conversely, how many of us IL researchers are using this approach? Is it an old hope or a new one? Is such connection obvious, or are practitioners too busy to realize that this is a good match? (p. 50).

PM have been used in L research, often driven by critical theory, for developing IL programs or activities in higher education (Webber & Johnson, 2000; Moore, 2000; Vezzosi, 2006; Machin-Mastromatteo, 2012), within schools (Mortimer, 2000), as a framework for evaluating IL instruction (Hearn, Tacchi, Foth & Lennie, 2009), among others. Moreover, in this age of social, new and participatory media, participatory approaches are logical choices when dealing with the integration or mediation of these technologies for their appropriation (McIntosh, 2010).

Pros and Cons of PM

Explaining the pros and cons of using PM on L research and practice is important to find out the possible hesitations or the eagerness that researchers and practitioners may have toward this integration. As the humanities and social sciences evolved, PM have also been improved during the last 70 years. PM are very closely related to a human perspective (Reason, 2003), which is defined in the literature as 'research with people' as opposed to the positivist 'research on people' (Altrichter & Gstettner, 1997).

The rich subjectivity of the human being is the point of interest of PM, however, some positivist or behaviorist researchers tend to dismiss them as being purely subjective and not serious research traditions (McNiff, Lomax & Whitehead, 2002; Herr & Anderson, 2015). Such a view against PM share similar in criticisms to those concerning the use of qualitative methodologies. For instance, the argument that participatory researchers do not have mathematical and statistics skills, which explains the use of such approaches. Issues of validity, trustworthiness and the number of participants in a participatory study are also highlighted against PM, even though not every methodological tradition can be evaluated under the same lenses and values of quantitative research; as for instance, the results of participatory research may be highly dependent on the contexts and cultures where the research took place and thus replicability of results is very challenging. Nevertheless, PM are favorable if they bring objectivity into the subjectivities it studies. Indeed, the issues of objectivity-subjectivity, validity, trustworthiness, and number of participants are of concern for participatory researchers, they have been carefully addressed, and strong ways to ensure validity and trustworthiness have been developed within these methodological traditions (e.g. Whitehead & McNiff, 2006; Herr & Anderson, 2015). Even so, apart from keeping these scientific values of trust, it is also important that participatory researchers control most of the variables they study and are transparent in the ways they report their methodological choices throughout the whole research process (Zuber-Skerritt, 1992; Whitehead & McNiff, 2006; Blair, 2010), in order to ensure that their results are trustworthy, valid, replicable and reliable. PM also demand researchers to maintain a deep ethical commitment, as ethical principles are among the most important issues regarding research trustworthiness; because numbers in quantitative research might be falsified or inaccurately analyzed as data from qualitative research.

The correct use of PM shares the same values with any other methodologies, they are valid if they are systematic, they must establish carefully their parameters, and they must closely follow their objectives. Research trustworthiness also implies conforming to

long-standing traditional values, which Machin-Mastromatteo, Lau & Virkus (2013) list as: a) keeping in mind that research should be replicable; b) research has to maintain logic regarding its structure, discourse and analysis throughout all its stages; c) there should be coincidences between the results of a given study and the results provided in the specialized literature; d) research should have the ultimate goal of seeking 'the truth', balancing the objective/subjective dichotomy; e) participants' profiles must be carefully detailed; and specifically for PM, f) researchers must clearly demonstrate how a state of betterment was achieved considering participants' practices or situations.

Methodology

The following two sections report the methodology and unpublished results from a questionnaire suggested in a previous article (Machin-Mastromatteo, Lau & Virkus, 2013). This questionnaire was conceived from a PAR approach, as all IL practitioners and researchers were invited to answer it, so findings would emerge from the participation of the community of stakeholders. We took the advantage of inviting researchers and practitioners during the first four editions of the European Conference on Information Literacy (ECIL). A larger number of practitioners was invited to participate by sending the questionnaire link through mailing lists and social media sites devoted to IL.

Although the questionnaire was promoted at a large international conference, through mailing lists, social media and during a four-year period (2013-2017), it was answered by 34 participants. Only 16 of them had previous experiences on the PAR-IL integration and just 8 participants provided significant answers to our open-ended questions. Hence, these issues seriously limited the amount of data available to analyze. Although when looking at the number of documents involving PM-L that are indexed in Scopus and that we have presented above, we have confirmed that this is a 'niche' research area with a relatively small number of academics (158 authors) publishing papers about it

The guiding research question used to develop the questionnaire was: in what ways can PAR contribute to the development of a research and practice IL agenda? Secondary research questions were:

- a) In what ways have IL practitioners profited from using participatory methodologies?;
- b) What are the main contributions of PAR in IL research and practice?; and
- c) To which degree have IL practitioners used and accepted PAR for their activities?

The questionnaire had two closed-ended profiling questions, such as asking about what is their field of knowledge and if they have dealt with PM in their L research and practice. Other questions required them to:

- provide a short account on their experiences and lessons learned using PM-L (if they have dealt with it);
- opine on whether they think that PM allow advancing L research and practice agenda;

- assess if PM are worthy to revise and retake or if they are out of touch with the times;
- state the important elements for advancing a PM-L research and practice agenda;
- assess if they think a PM-L perspective would be favorable and how it would contribute to development (e.g. individuals, policies, countries) and the LIS field.

Results

The profiling questions included in the questionnaire allowed to identify the background fields of the 34 participants: 20 had a LIS background, 10 were from the Social Sciences, 2 from Engineering, 1 from Education and 1 from Law. Regarding having experience with PM in their L research and practice, 16 participants replied 'Yes' and 18 'No'. The following subsections summarize participants' answers to the other questions.

Experiences and lessons learned using PM-L

Although 16 participants stated having experience with PM in their L research and practice, only 8 of them answered an open-ended question requesting them to share their experiences and lessons learned using PM-L. Seven participants used with their users or students, one for developing DL, four participants used it for developing IL, one used PM-L for their lectures mediated through technology and the other was a thesis supervisor on a research that used AR. The remaining participant stated to have been using PM-L with their research group. Relevant lessons learned by the participants by using PM-L include:

- It is a suitable methodology to develop information competences and information practices, including seeking, access, use, and dealing with scientific information.
- It allows mediating and reconciling theory and practice through the development of learning activities integrating both, as well as account participants' attitudes, perceptions, beliefs and knowledge, such integration may enhance learning experiences.
- Within a classroom, it is possible to observe collaborative work both in digital environments and in person.
- PM-L has a strong connection with critical pedagogy.
- It allows exploring individual perceptions and ways of doing things, to determine the most appropriate models and best practices.
- 'Badania w działaniu', AR in Polish, allowed a research team at a Polish university to enhance cooperation, develop research skills and theoretical foundations.
- PM have an interventional goal, it might help to change social practices, including teaching practices such as moving from a positivist model of education based on the transmission of information to one based on a deepened reflection on individuals' own practices (defined as ways of acting), which are then developed and reviewed by learners.

One participant highlighted the potential of PM-L, which can be perceived in: understanding the context of individual's information practices, building dialogical relationships between the learners and the teachers-researchers-learners (collapse the teacher-student dichotomy), solving hidden problems that have not been articulated in the curricula, the creation of a community of practitioners without a dominating voice.

In what ways do PM allow advancing literacies' research and practice agendas

Eight participants answered this question. Their insights included the following perspectives that may allow PM to advance L research and practice agendas:

- PM may advance the agenda by having a real and lasting impact in research participants, as many methods center just in the study of perceptions and do not entail actions and improvements in research subjects, as PM do.
- PM allow designing academic projects that consider regional contexts.
- PM take into consideration the constant assessment of all research stakeholders.
- When used for L training, PM allow such a training to be more personalized and contextualized to participants' culture and needs.
- Given PM's emancipatory potential, it could be applied for the research and development of themes such as freedom, comfort, the limits of privacy in Internet, and the grey market in scientific communication.
- PM has the possibility of increasing the pertinence and relevance of L research, which is unfortunately dominated by quantitative methods.
- PM offer the opportunity of conducting in-depth qualitative research that centers on the study of practices.

Regarding participants' assessment of whether or not PM are worthy to revise and retake or if they are out of touch with the times, this was asked first through a closed-ended question seeking a positive or negative answer. This question was answered by just 10 participants, nine indicated the former positive statement, while one participant indicated the latter statement, that PM is out of touch with the times. The second part of this question required participants to justify their above response. Only six participants answered, in particular, one researcher's answer is worth quoting in full:

In my opinion PAR is the method coherent for all times. Especially for researcher who defines learning as the social practice. PAR – considering its interventional goal – is a tool that does not age. Human learns by analyzing and changing his/her actions.

Participants' general arguments for revising and retaking PM in L research and practice lean toward the possibility of developing promising research beyond the traditional contexts, centered in the context of each region or country, and with a more qualitative focus.

Important elements for advancing a PM-L research and practice agenda

Regarding the topic of the important elements for advancing a PM-L research and practice agenda, six participants provided responses that can be summarized as:

- developing a larger number of studies using such methodologies, leaving behind the traditional models, in order to offer results that go beyond being mere diagnostics, and studies that go beyond "beyond the behavioral assessment of attitudes, which are collated with the patterns of desired attitudes";
- incorporate PM to education policies from primary schooling levels to higher education;
- conduct a large number of local studies and launch international seminars to evaluate experiences, which allow undertaking international collaboration under the spirit of PM in order to enrich them; and
- conduct research with a deeper engagement, participation and experience from research participants and highlighting the pedagogical angle of L, which is often omitted in the available research.

Contributions from a PM-L perspective

Participants were asked in what ways they think a PM-L perspective would be favorable. Three of them provided answers: a) to register impact indicators and not just behavioral indicators; b) to incorporate the development of L from primary schooling; and c) to have a larger engagement from the communities in which researchers and practitioners work with.

The questionnaire asked participants to provide their insights about the contributions of a PM-L perspective in two different questions, one required participants to explain possible contributions toward development, while the second was aimed toward the LIS field. Regarding PM-L' contributions for development, five participants commented that improving participants' practices help them grow personally, professionally and allows them to be more literate, of which to be literate is perhaps the best means that each individual, collective or society can contribute to the development of a given country or a region. However, one participant pointed out that in order to have an impact on development, PM-L must be inserted in education policies. Regarding the contributions of a PM-L perspective to the LIS field, five participants provided answers, which included: a) turning the information professional into a manager that is directly engaged with learning processes, and not in isolation from the library; b) training professionals specialized in PM and L research, so their work should be considered academic and not administrative; c) revitalizing reference services and librarians' educational mediation; and d) in the participants' own words: "our profession needs good research, so maybe PM could become 'flagship methods' for literacies research?" Given participants' answers and the diverse roles that LIS professionals are assuming in their institutions, there may be a need to ensure that LIS education includes the training and development of competences on three main areas that are related to the present discussion, namely: education, L, and PM.

Conclusion

This article provides a step toward the revision and further adoption of PM for L research and practice. All systematic research that is properly carried out and takes into account the perspectives and even the input from its participants is valid, it can advance our understanding around L and contribute to its theory, research and practice. The intention of a paper such as the present is to explore, seek to understand, and establish the possible contributions PM-L research agenda can bring to the LIS profession, under the understanding that any systematic methodology may help the advance of L as fields of study, apart from justifying that PM are a perfect but not explicit fit through the cited literature, the analysis of Scopus data and the researchers and practitioners that participated in the questionnaire.

We have provided a brief overview of using PM on L research and practice, as well as gone a step forward in formally establishing the PM-L connection and research agenda for other researchers and practitioners. Its pros and cons were explained, as well as its possibilities, characteristics and the contributions of the PM-L research agenda. Given the analyzed Scopus data, we could confirm that this is a valid emerging research area that has just started to be developed during the past 17 years and that really started gaining traction after 2006. The questionnaire we used, although it had few respondents helped us confirm some of the characteristics and issues of the topics we have focused upon, as they are also reported in the pertinent literature. Further research may include analyzing the available 113 documents on PM-L and interviewing the 158 researchers that published these documents (many of them already participated in the questionnaire presented in this article). This would allow expanding the present analysis and defining, in a very precise manner, this research and practice area. Further research on a PM-L agenda may also include: providing lines of research, identifying tendencies for its growth and development, and establishing it as the *de facto* methodologies for conducting L research and practice.

Note

It is noteworthy to comment that this participant, from a Latin American country, stressed this need for librarians' work to be recognized as academic and not administrative. In Latin America, is very common to see that all library staff are considered administrative positions, regardless of their level of study, competences or the work they do at an organization; they are seen as employees that do not study a formal university profession, something that is worsened by the fact that Latin American organizations traditionally employ staff with barely a high-school degree to work on their libraries. This organizational perspective, which seems to be culturally stagnated, is often contested by librarians with masters and doctoral degrees, but with not much luck.

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